

Master in Music and Sound Computing

Universitat Pompeu Fabra

Meditation and Solo Singing as a Therapeutic
Intervention for Anxiety and Depression

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August 2024

**Universitat
Pompeu Fabra**
Barcelona

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Dedication

To those I've loved and lost this year.

Acknowledgments

I would like to thank my advisor, Rafael Ramírez, for his insights, advice and care throughout this in depth learning experience. I would like to thank Suvi Häärä for being a source of inspiration, for working with me on the experiments we conducted together and for being a participant in one of the experiments I organized. I would like to thank my friends, family and teachers in Barcelona and all around the world for being there for me and supporting me during a tough year. I would like to thank Lily, my dog, for sitting next to me while I wrote this thesis.

Abstract

This thesis explores the impact of solo singing and meditation on mental health, focusing specifically on their effects on anxiety, depression, and overall emotional well-being. The study employs electroencephalography (EEG) to measure brain wave activity and the Positive and Negative Affect Schedule (PANAS) to assess mood changes before and after singing and meditation sessions. By integrating these methods, the research aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of how solo singing and meditation influence both physiological responses in the brain and self-reported emotional states.

The research was conducted at Universitat Pompeu Fabra, with data collected from participants during voice lessons and meditation exercises. The EEG sensors captured brain wave data, particularly focusing on alpha waves, which are associated with relaxation and reduced anxiety, during both activities. The PANAS questionnaire provided additional insights into participants' emotional states, allowing for a comparative analysis of the effects of singing and meditation on pre- and post-session affect.

The findings suggest that while both solo singing and meditation have the potential to positively impact mental health, the data were inconclusive in fully validating the hypotheses. Although trends indicated an increase in alpha wave activity and improvements in PANAS scores, these results were not consistent across all participants, suggesting variability in individual responses. Consequently, while the study supports the potential therapeutic benefits of solo singing and meditation, further research with a larger sample size and refined methodologies is necessary to fully validate these findings.

This study contributes to the ongoing exploration of music therapy and mindfulness practices, highlighting the need for more rigorous investigations into their effects on mental health. The implications of these findings suggest that while solo singing and meditation show promise as non-pharmacological interventions for mental health issues, more conclusive evidence is required to substantiate their efficacy.

Keywords: solo singing, meditation, music therapy, mental health, EEG, PANAS, anxiety, depression

1. Introduction

1.1. Meditation

Meditation is a widely practiced technique for achieving mental clarity and emotional balance, often associated with specific patterns of brain wave activity. Recent advancements in signal processing and electroencephalography (EEG) have enabled researchers to capture these brain wave patterns in real-time, providing deeper insights into the neural dynamics of meditative states. By analyzing EEG signals, it is possible to extract meaningful features that reflect the meditator's mental state. This study explores the innovative integration of EEG signal processing with sound synthesis, using brain waves generated during meditation to control a synthesizer. This approach includes an auditory feedback mechanism for meditators and addresses the intersection between neuroscience, musical expression and real-time brain-computer interaction.

In order to learn more about EEG signals and systems to analyze brain waves, I developed a system that would use EEG data to produce various sounds. “The EEG consists of measurements of varying heights (amplitude) and wavelengths (frequency). Frequency refers to the number of times a waveform rises and falls in one second, and it is measured in hertz (Hz), or cycles per second (cps).” (van der Kolk) This is similar to sound waves so the features of EEG signals can be extracted in the same ways as features of audio signals.

The sounds produced by the synthesizer correlates to the amount of alpha waves present in the EEG data in comparison to the other waves produced. This study allows for exploration of EEG signals and how they can be analyzed with regards to feature extraction, time-based variability, and sensitivity. The objective was to develop an auditory feedback mechanism using real-time EEG data and a synthesizer. In essence, a neurofeedback device was developed to sonify brain waves during meditation to create a preference towards alpha waves using neurofeedback techniques. As Bessel van der Kolk explains in *The Body Keeps The Score*:

“Feedback provides the brain with a mirror of its own function: the oscillations and rhythms that underpin the currents and crosscurrents of the mind. Neurofeedback nudges the brain to make more of some frequencies and less of others, creating new

patterns that enhance its natural complexity and its bias toward self-regulation” (van der Kolk, 2014).

Exploring neurofeedback and its benefits is eye-opening. It allows for a deeper exploration of the possibilities of EEG-based studies on mental health. It has been shown that people can be trained to produce certain brain waves, and as the study suggests, one way to do this is with sound.

Performing research for this study produced valuable insight; however, it was recognized that using data from EEG signals might not always produce statistically significant results due to various challenges. “EEG data are generally only available in small quantities, they are high dimensional with a poor signal-to-noise ratio, and there is considerable variability between individual subjects and recording sessions” (Stober, 2018). Nonetheless, understanding and working with these limitations allowed for the refinement of the neurofeedback approach.

In a study performed with a Tibetan Monastery, “results showed that concentrative meditation elicited more numerous and marked changes in the EEG power compared to analytical meditation, and mainly in the form of an increase in the theta, alpha, and beta frequency ranges” (Neri et al., 2023). Concentrative meditation, also known as Focused Attention Meditation (FAM), involves focusing the mind on a single object, thought, or sensation, such as the breath, a mantra, or a specific visual object. The primary goal of this practice is to develop sustained attention and concentration, enhancing the ability to focus the mind and minimize distractions. Analytical meditation, on the other hand, involves the process of systematic thinking and reflection on specific topics or concepts. It is often used to explore philosophical, ethical, or spiritual questions and to gain deeper understanding and insight. Both types of meditation help with “strengthening the ability to be aware of thought processes, emotions, and the body” (Neri et al., 2023).

In the study I present in this thesis, concentrative meditation is used, and the “object” is the sound produced by the synthesizer. Long-term participation in this type of meditation can result in structural changes, such as increased cortical thickness in regions like the prefrontal cortex and insula (Lee et al., 2018). This is supported by van der Kolk’s observation that:

“Alpha waves (8-12 Hz) are accompanied by a sense of peace and calm. They are familiar to anyone who has learned mindfulness meditation” (van der Kolk, 2014). These changes contribute to improvements in attention, processing, and performance, which are some of the known benefits of meditation. People often meditate not just to get better at meditation but to improve their overall quality of life, and this is the scientific background that explains these benefits.

Exploring neurofeedback opens up many possibilities. As mentioned above, mental states can be induced using a neurofeedback approach. Relaxation can be induced to help people experiencing anxiety disorders. Focus can be enhanced to help people with ADHD. Higher energy brain waves can be stimulated to treat depression. “Modulations of alpha and theta oscillations have been associated with positive psychological outcomes, including reduced levels of anxiety, depression, anger, and confusion, alongside heightened awareness, perceptual clarity, and introspective attention” (Neri et al., 2023). Neurofeedback thus holds significant potential for therapeutic applications, as van der Kolk suggests:

“Once the brain has been trained to produce different patterns of electrical communication, no further treatment is necessary, in contrast to drugs, which do not change fundamental brain activity and work only as long as the patient keeps taking them” (van der Kolk, 2014).

After becoming familiar with the power of neurofeedback, brain waves as well as incorporating previous knowledge of meditation, a hypothesis was formed. The hypothesis for this part of the study is that using a neurofeedback device will assist with meditation and condition the participant to produce greater levels of alpha waves than if they were meditating without the neurofeedback device as well as cause the participant to self-report an increase in positive effect and a decrease in negative effect.

1.2. Singing

Singing is a universal form of musical expression that has been a part of human culture for thousands of years. Music and singing are integral to various social, religious, and therapeutic practices across different cultures. Scientific research into the psychological and physiological benefits of singing has grown significantly in recent decades. However, there are countless gaps to be filled and research questions to be further studied.

Numerous studies suggest that singing can significantly impact mental health by reducing stress, enhancing mood, and improving cognitive functions. It can promote relaxation, help individuals cope with tough situations, as well as energize the mind and body.

Singing has been shown to reduce levels of stress hormones like cortisol and increase levels of endorphins, which are natural mood lifters. It can promote relaxation and help individuals unwind after a stressful day. Singing releases dopamine, a neurotransmitter associated with pleasure and reward. This can lead to improved mood and well-being.

Despite the growing body of evidence supporting the mental health benefits of solo singing, there is a need for more comprehensive and systematic investigations into how solo singing activities affect psychological well-being. Previous research has focused on various aspects of singing, but it is difficult to track down a centralized effort to build upon studies that focus on the benefits of solo singing. There have not been many studies that focus directly on solo singing. However, there is a large amount of research in related fields that can be explored in relation to the mental health benefits of solo singing.

For instance, Cooper (2017) demonstrated that solo singing can significantly enhance immune function by increasing levels of Immunoglobulin A (IgA), an antibody blood protein crucial for the immune system. “One study recorded a 150% increase in IgA in 10 solo singers that were monitored over a 10-week period” (Cooper). This finding suggests that solo singing may help reduce stress and improve overall well-being, as elevated IgA levels are associated with greater positivity and relaxation.

The act of singing not only provides immediate emotional relief but also contributes to long-term mental health benefits. Research has indicated that solo singing can have a unique impact on emotional regulation. The rhythmic nature of singing, combined with deep breathing techniques, can create a meditative effect, further enhancing relaxation and reducing anxiety. It is important to consider the physiological changes that occur during singing. As stated, singing involves controlled breathing, which can activate the parasympathetic nervous system, responsible for rest and digestion. This activation can counteract the effects of the sympathetic nervous system, which governs the fight-or-flight response, leading to a state of relaxation and reduced stress. Understanding these physiological mechanisms will provide a more comprehensive view of how solo singing influences mental health. Also, the social aspect of singing, even in solo practices, can

foster a sense of connection to oneself and a greater understanding of personal emotions. Unlike group singing, which often involves social interaction and shared emotional experiences, solo singing allows for a more introspective and personal exploration of emotions. This individual focus can lead to a deeper understanding and processing of one's feelings, which is crucial for emotional healing and growth.

The primary objectives of this study are to:

1. Assess the impact of solo singing on brain wave activity using EEG signals.
2. Investigate changes in mood and emotional well-being before and after solo singing sessions using the PANAS questionnaire.
3. Compare results to past research in both the fields of singing as well as mental health in attempts to fill gaps, assess hypotheses, and propose future research.

This research is significant because it aims to deepen our understanding of the mental health benefits of solo singing, which could inform the development of therapeutic interventions and wellness programs. By studying the specific effects of solo singing on brain wave activity, mood, and cognition, this study may contribute to the broader field of music therapy and provide evidence-based practices for improving mental health through participatory music-making. The results of this study could also highlight the importance of integrating solo musical activities into daily routines to promote overall well-being. This study will explore whether solo singing can create immersive experiences and whether these experiences contribute to the mental health benefits associated with singing.

The scope of this study is limited to adult participants engaged in solo singing activities. It will not cover other forms of musical engagement such as group singing, listening to music, or playing musical instruments. Potential limitations include the self-reported nature of mood assessments and the variability in individual responses to solo singing activities. Additionally, technical difficulties with the EEG sensors may result in some data being discarded. Hypothesis: Solo singing will raise self-reported positive affects, lower self-reported negative affects, as well as raise the ratio of alpha brain waves in comparison to the full spectrum of brain wave frequencies.

1.3. Electroencephalogram (EEG)

In order to begin designing my hypothesis and procedure, I learned more about EEG signals and data that could be retrieved using EEG signals. An electroencephalogram (EEG) is a recording of the oscillations of electric potentials in the brain, sometimes referred to as a “window of the mind”. (Kučikienė) EEGs signals change rapidly in response to the brain waves produced by the person attached to the sensors. “Although brain activity is spontaneous and does not depend on specific sensory stimuli, it might be easily altered by them, and these changes can also be seen in the findings of EEGs” (Kučikienė) Because brain waves can be altered so quickly, they provide insights into quick changes in mood. The frequencies of waves recorded through EEGs can indicate various attributes of a person’s mental state. While these waves appear on a continuous range of frequencies, they can be grouped together. The following is a standard way to group brain waves:

“Depending on the frequency, waves can be categorized as delta (1–4 Hz), theta (4–8 Hz), alpha (8–13 Hz) (which is sometimes divided into alpha 1 (8–10 Hz) and alpha 2 (11–13 Hz)) and beta (more than 13 Hz). Another category of very high (30– 40 Hz) frequencies is referred to as gamma waves” (Kučikienė). A figure summarizing these ideas can be found in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Brain wave categories, attributes and their associated frequencies

Image: Isabel, C. (n.d.). The 5 types of brain waves: What they mean, how they help us. *DIY Genius*. Retrieved from <https://www.diygenius.com/the-5-types-of-brain-waves/>

1.4. Positive and Negative Affect Schedule (PANAS)

The Positive and Negative Affect Schedule (PANAS) is a self-report measure of affect, designed to evaluate an individual's positive and negative emotional states. It is “one of the most widely used scales to measure mood or emotion” (Tran). The PANAS consists of 20 items, with 10 items assessing positive affect (PA) and 10 items assessing negative affect (NA). Each item is rated on a scale from 1 to 5, resulting in scores ranging from 10 to 50 for both PA and NA. (Watson)

To calculate the total scores, researchers sum the ratings of the 10 positive items for the PA score and the 10 negative items for the NA score (Watson). Higher PA scores indicate a greater presence of positive affect, while lower NA scores suggest a lesser presence of negative affect.

Regarding the validity of the PANAS, both convergent and divergent validity have been demonstrated through correlations with measures of depression, anxiety, and personality. Positive Affect (PA) scores show strong inverse correlations with depression measures and moderate correlations with anxiety measures. Conversely, Negative Affect (NA) scores exhibit strong positive correlations with symptoms of depression and anxiety.

The reliability of the PANAS is assessed using Cronbach's alpha, with values indicating the internal consistency of the scale. Suggested guidelines for interpreting these alpha coefficients are: unacceptable ($<.7$), fair ($.7-.8$), good ($.8-.9$), and excellent ($>.9$) (Watson).

The following positive and negative emotions were used to evaluate the PANAS scores of the participants.

- Positive affects: interested, excited, strong, enthusiastic, proud, alert, inspired, determined, attentive, active
- Negative affects: distressed, upset, guilty, scared, hostile, irritable, ashamed, nervous, jittery, afraid

An example of the questionnaire is shown here in Figure 2.

	Very slightly or not at all	A little	Moderately	Quite a bit	Extremely
Interested	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Distressed	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Excited	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Upset	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Strong	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Guilty	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Scared	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Hostile	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Enthusiastic	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Proud	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Irritable	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Alert	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Ashamed	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Inspired	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Nervous	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Determined	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Attentive	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Jittery	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Afraid	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Figure 2: Positive and Negative Affect Schedule (PANAS)

Image: Watson, D., Clark, L. A., & Tellegen, A. (1988). Development and validation of brief measures of positive and negative affect: The PANAS scales. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 54(6), 1063-1070.

2. State Of The Art

2.1. Meditation

Meditation is a simple practice available to all, which can reduce stress, increase calmness and clarity and promote happiness (Gelles). It involves paying close attention to the present moment, and its benefits can be realized relatively quickly. This chapter explores the current state of research on how meditation affects brain waves, highlighting various physiological, emotional, and cognitive outcomes associated with different types of meditation practices.

Meditation has been shown to induce specific physiological changes, including alterations in breath rate, skin conductance, and EEG patterns. These changes are indicative of the profound impact meditation can have on the brain and body.

Meditation practices are associated with a range of positive emotional outcomes, including increased happiness, calmness, and clarity (Gelles). The regular practice of meditation enhances self-awareness and emotional regulation, allowing individuals to manage their emotions more effectively. "Meditation is a way to train the mind. Most of the time, our minds are wandering — we're thinking about the future, dwelling on the past, worrying, fantasizing, fretting, or daydreaming. Meditation brings us back to the present moment, and gives us the tools we need to be less stressed, calmer and kinder to ourselves and others" (Gelles).

EEG, or electroencephalogram, is a recording of the oscillations of electric potentials in the brain. During meditation, particularly Transcendental Meditation (TM), there is an increase in frontal EEG alpha coherence (8–12 Hz), which is associated with improved psychological functioning (Fred). Research indicates that brainwaves can be altered by various external stimuli, with auditory stimuli, especially music, being among the most impactful (Kučikienė).

Concentrative meditation, also known as Focused Attention Meditation (FAM) in Tibetan Buddhism, entails voluntarily focusing attention on a chosen object, like the breath. This practice is related to increased alpha and theta power, which are associated with enhanced awareness, relaxed alertness, and well-being (Lomas et al., 2015). Enhanced theta power, in particular, has been correlated with the deepening of the

meditative state and plays a critical role in non-ordinary states of consciousness (Piarulli et al., 2018; Zaccaro et al., 2021, 2022). As van der Kolk notes, “alpha-theta training is a particularly fascinating neurofeedback procedure because it can induce the sorts of hypnagogic states—the essence of hypnotic trance” (van der Kolk, 2014).

Alpha oscillations play a significant role in attentional modulation and excitability control. During concentrative meditation, the enhancement of alpha power has been linked to inwardly directed attention, reflecting an active inhibitory mechanism that suppresses irrelevant and distracting inputs, thereby prioritizing task-relevant information (Fuxe and Snyder, 2011; Hanslmayr et al., 2011). According to a study, the augmentation of alpha and theta band power, predominantly across frontal regions, aligns with findings from systematic reviews on contemplative practices (Fell et al., 2010; Lomas et al., 2015; Lee et al., 2018). "Alpha oscillations have been linked with heightened interoceptive attention, observed not only during meditation but also during other attentional tasks where participants internally shift focus, such as toward heartbeat sensations during cardiac interoceptive tasks" (Villena-González et al., 2017).

Additionally, concentrative meditation is related to increased posterior gamma power, while no clear changes were found for beta activity (Lee et al., 2018). The presence of high gamma, alpha, and theta activity may indicate a state of consciousness characterized by heightened awareness and perceptual clarity (Fumoto et al., 2004; Yu et al., 2011).

High psychosocial stress causes brain regions involved in memory and emotions, such as the hippocampus, amygdala, and prefrontal cortex, to undergo structural remodeling, impairing memory and increasing anxiety and aggression (Fred). Transcendental Meditation practice has been reported to decrease the effects of previous stressful experiences and help individuals function better in stressful situations (Fred). This aligns with van der Kolk’s observation that “calming the fear center decreases trauma-based problems and improves executive functioning” (van der Kolk, 2014).

The practice of meditation has also been associated with structural changes in the brain. For instance, long-term meditation practitioners show increased cortical thickness in brain areas related to attention, interoception, and sensory processing (Hölzel et al., 2011). These structural changes are thought to underlie some of the cognitive and emotional benefits of meditation. Van der Kolk emphasizes this point:

“Patients need help to change the habitual brain patterns created by trauma and its aftermath. When the fear patterns relax, the brain becomes less susceptible to automatic stress reactions and better able to focus on ordinary events” (van der Kolk, 2014).

Meditation is often utilized as a stress reduction technique and a way to strengthen oneself mentally. It trains the mind to focus on the present moment, reducing distractions and enhancing mental clarity (Gelles). The practice of meditation has been shown to reduce anxiety more effectively compared to other clinical relaxation methods (Fred). Meditation has been shown to enhance cognitive flexibility and creativity, allowing individuals to think more freely and solve problems more effectively. "Meditation can be a demanding activity that requires considerable concentration and practice, and so is capable of creating a sense of 'absorption' or 'flow' allowing the practitioner to escape from other preoccupations" (Clift).

Regular meditation practice can lead to greater neural efficiency, with the brain using fewer resources to accomplish cognitive tasks. This efficiency is reflected in changes in brainwave patterns, such as increased alpha coherence and reduced beta activity, indicating a more streamlined and effective neural processing state. "The specific increase of alpha power during concentrative meditation may be elucidated in light of numerous prior studies exploring the interplay between alpha oscillations and inwardly directed attention regulation, sensory processing, and task performance" (Fell et al., 2010). Van der Kolk further notes that “Neurofeedback training can improve creativity, athletic control, and inner awareness, even in people who already are highly accomplished” (van der Kolk, 2014).

The presence of background music contributes to attentional performance, both for musicians and non-musicians, by providing a stable and predictable auditory environment that supports concentration and focus during meditation (NCBI). "Our findings suggest that the addition of simple-structured, soothing, lyrics-free music helps enhance the positive emotions and does not interfere with the meditation process" (NCBI). Music creates an ideal environment for meditation by regulating arousal and improving mood, ensuring the practitioner's attention is maintained (NCBI). This is supported by findings that background music contributes to attentional performance and helps regulate the

practitioner's arousal to an appropriate level during meditation (NCBI). "The inclusion of background music in Loving-Kindness Meditation can regulate the practitioner's arousal to an appropriate level during the process, and the positive emotions induced by music counteract the psychological resource consumption caused by listening to music" (NCBI).

Meditation practices, through specific mental training, can lead to increased activation of cognitive control areas. This is evident in the decrease in amygdala function and increase in the activation of cognitive control areas when listening to unfamiliar music with steady, simple rhythms during mindfulness meditation (ResearchGate). "Descriptions of mindfulness vary, but they all include the process of focusing attention on an 'object' (e.g., breath, body sensations, or image), being distracted from the object, noticing and acknowledging the distraction, and returning attention back to the object" (ResearchGate).

The effects of meditation on brain waves can vary depending on the type of meditation practiced and the experience level of the practitioner. For instance, skilled meditation practitioners may prefer meditation without background music, while beginners might find music without a specific melody helpful (NCBI). Music with a simple structure and predictable harmonies can support meditation by regulating arousal and enhancing positive emotions without interfering with the meditation process (NCBI). Research has shown that non-musicians found simpler audio stimuli more effective for mindfulness meditation, while more complex stimuli were preferred and found more useful by musicians (ResearchGate). "Beginners with no prior experience in meditation tend to prefer music without a specific melody" (NCBI).

Overall, the current state of research indicates that meditation offers numerous benefits, including physiological, emotional, and cognitive improvements. These benefits include changes in brain wave patterns, particularly in the alpha and theta ranges. Understanding these effects can help optimize meditation practices for different individuals and contexts, enhancing their overall effectiveness. By leveraging the mental health benefits of meditation, we can develop more effective strategies for promoting well-being and quality of life. Further research is needed to explore the specific mechanisms underlying these benefits and to tailor meditation practices to individual

needs and preferences. Given the growing interest in meditation as a tool for stress reduction and mental enhancement, continued investigation into its effects on brain waves will be crucial for advancing our understanding and application of this practice.

2.2. Singing

The exploration of the mental health benefits of singing has gained more attention over recent decades. However, the topic is still not very popular or thoroughly researched. This chapter aims to provide an overview of the current state of research on how singing influences psychological well-being, stress levels, and overall mental health. Because specific research on solo singing as a therapeutic intervention has not been extensively reported on, I also collected information on adjacent topics related to group singing, immune responses to singing, the effects of singing on populations of different backgrounds, as well as a person's physiological and biological responses to singing.

Singing is accessible to people of all ages and backgrounds. Systematic scientific research into the mental health benefits of singing began to gain more popularity in the late 20th century, with early studies focusing on therapeutic applications in clinical settings. These foundational studies paved the way for more rigorous investigations into the broader impacts of singing on mental health. Since then, there have been attempts to keep track of various research done in the field to promote further studies that build off of past work.

Recent research has expanded our understanding of the psychological and physiological effects of singing. Studies such as those by Fancourt et al. (2015) have explored how singing influences stress-related biomarkers like cortisol and cytokine activity. "Singing was associated with a decrease in cortisol and increase in cytokine activity" (Fancourt, 2015). It has been shown that "low-stress performance conditions lead to reductions in cortisol and that high-stress conditions lead to increases" (Aufegger). Singing not only improves mental health but also enhances physiological resilience, potentially offering a protective effect against stress-related illnesses.

Singing has been integrated into therapeutic interventions for mental health conditions, including depression, anxiety, and PTSD. Cooper's research demonstrated significant increases in Immunoglobulin A (IgA) levels among solo singers, suggesting enhanced immune function and reduced stress. "Immunoglobulin A (IgA) is an antibody

blood protein that is an important part of the immune system. We make IgA and other types of antibodies to help fight off sickness" (Cooper). "One study recorded a 150% increase in IgA in 10 solo singers that were monitored over a 10-week period" (Cooper). Elevated IgA levels are associated with greater positivity and relaxation. This suggests that the act of singing can have far-reaching effects beyond immediate emotional benefits, potentially strengthening the body's overall immune response and, as touched on before, resilience to illness.

Clift and Hancox (2010) highlighted the social and emotional benefits of group singing, emphasizing its role in enhancing social connections and community well-being. Group singing has been associated with improved mood and reduced stress. Clift noted, "Music is one of the defining features of our human nature, and singing is a form of musical participation and expression open to everyone." The communal aspect of group singing can foster a sense of belonging and support, which is particularly beneficial for individuals experiencing loneliness or social isolation. However, while group singing has its benefits, the focus on solo singing in this study allows for an examination of the personal, introspective benefits that may be overlooked in group settings.

The advent of digital platforms has enabled virtual choirs and online singing interventions, broadening the accessibility of singing-based therapies. These digital interventions can make singing accessible to individuals who might not have the opportunity to participate in person due to geographic, health, or social constraints. The expansion of virtual singing communities provides new opportunities for research into the mental health benefits of both solo and group singing in digital formats. As technology continues to evolve, it will be important to explore how these new platforms can be used to maximize the therapeutic benefits of singing. This study does not include experiments related to singing in digital formats, but it is another way to make voice lessons even more accessible.

Clift's research emphasizes that singing can stimulate cognitive capacities such as attention, concentration, memory, and learning. It also promotes emotional release, reduces stress, and increases feelings of joy and arousal. "Singing can be a demanding activity which requires considerable concentration and practice, and so is capable of creating a sense of 'absorption' or 'flow' allowing the singer to escape from other

preoccupations" (Clift, 2010). Many individuals report feeling happier and more energized after singing. Grape's research indicated that amateur singers experience more well-being and joy after singing lessons compared to professional singers. "The results indicated marked differences between professionals and amateurs with regard to physiological and emotional states. The professionals were more physiologically fit for singing, but did not experience the same well-being as amateurs seemed to do" (Grape). This suggests that singing, especially for those not doing it professionally, might offer more substantial mental health benefits. "Making music led to greater modulation of several different emotions, including happiness, than watching, listening, or an audio control" (Fancourt). These findings highlight the importance of singing as an accessible and effective means of enhancing emotional and cognitive well-being. In a gender related study, multiple studies measured that "women consistently express stronger wellbeing experiences associated with singing." (Stephen Clift) While these findings are interesting and have been reported on through thorough studies, there are many research gaps and challenges related to studying the mental health benefits of singing, especially with the necessity to study human participants.

Differences in study designs make it challenging to draw consistent conclusions about the effects of singing. While some studies focus on group singing, others explore solo singing or compare singing to other forms of musical engagement. The lack of standardization across studies makes it difficult to compare results directly. "Only four articles attempt to compare different modes of delivery, despite there being significantly increased relaxation found when participants sang rather than just listened to singing" (Fancourt). "Physically making music will lead to a greater modulation in emotion than watching or listening to music" (Fancourt). This finding underscores the importance of actively participating in music, rather than passively listening, to maximize its mental health benefits. The act of singing itself, particularly in a solo context, may engage the brain and body in ways that passive listening cannot, leading to more profound psychological and physiological benefits.

In a few studies "it can be seen that mood changes before and after the singing lesson. However, the research fails to consider which changes in mood can be associated with singing in particular or generally participating in a musical activity" (Clift). This variability underscores the need for more rigorous and standardized research

methodologies to better understand the specific effects of solo singing. In essence, few studies have compared different modes of musical engagement, such as singing versus listening to music, despite evidence suggesting that active music-making leads to greater emotional modulation.

The way each person in the study is affected by solo singing can be highly variable based on their preconceived notions of music and singing along with the extent of their previous experience creating or listening to music. Understanding how different contexts and individual differences influence the benefits of singing remains a challenge. This variability can also be influenced by cultural factors, as different cultures may have varying relationships with music and singing. Future research should consider these individual and cultural differences to better understand how solo singing can be optimized for mental health benefits across diverse populations.

Research also needs to account for placebo effects, as physiological parameters can be influenced by psychological and social factors. “Research demonstrating the reality of placebo effects in clinical pharmacological trials clearly contradicts any assumption that physiological parameters are immune to psychological or social influence” (Clift). The awareness of participating in a study, combined with the expectation of positive outcomes, can significantly influence the results. Researchers must design studies that minimize these effects to accurately measure the true impact of solo singing on mental health.

There has not been extensive research on the effects of singing on mental health compared to other areas of study relating to sound and music. However, there have been some relevant studies and findings related to the field. Some studies focused more on the effects of group singing, in which the positive effects of socialization and participation in a group must be taken into account. However, I wanted to focus on the biological effects of singing itself and decided to focus on solo singing. Some studies have focused on the biological impact of singing with regards to physiological indications (saliva, heart rate, immune response) and were taken into account as well, along with previous general research related to the topic. However, I wanted to study the mental health impacts of singing and decided to use EEG (electroencephalogram) sensors to retrieve my data. As discussed previously, “an electroencephalogram (EEG) is a recording of the oscillations

of electric potentials in the brain” (Kučkienė). The use of EEG in this study will allow for a more objective measure of brain wave activity, complementing self-reported data on mood and emotional well-being.

Overall, current state of research highlights the significant mental health benefits of solo singing, including stress reduction, mood enhancement, cognitive stimulation, and immune system support. This study aims to contribute to this field by combining psychological and self-reported data to provide more insight on solo singing's impact on mental health. As research continues to evolve, understanding the nuanced effects of solo singing on different populations and contexts will further enhance its application in promoting mental health and well-being.

3. Methods

3.1. Meditation

The same person I collaborated with in order to collect data for the voice lessons experiment, Suvi, agreed to be the participant for this study. The experiment took place in an office at UPF. Two other classmates, Anmol and Robin, assisted with the testing of the neurofeedback device and helped with troubleshooting throughout the experiment, keeping an eye on the computers to notice any inconsistencies or disconnections of the sensors while I sat with Suvi for the experiment. I explained the experiment to Suvi and we placed the EEG headset on her. We took some time to make sure all of the connections were made and all of the necessary parts of the headset were receiving signal from Suvi's brain. Once the troubleshooting was complete, I gave Suvi the same PANAS questionnaire used in the voice lessons experiment.

As discussed previously, research shows links to increased power in alpha brain waves and meditative states (Neri). In a study conducted using EEG signals, authors determined that noticeable differences in certain types of brain waves could be found after different periods of time meditating. "The required stimulation durations were either six or ten minutes for theta, five minutes for alpha, and 15 minutes for gamma entrainment." (*Ingendoh*) It was decided to test the neurofeedback device in durations of 5 minutes and search for differences in alpha waves.

During the study, the participant meditated for 5 minutes with and without the neurofeedback synthesizer, answering questions before and after each meditation attempt. The meditation instructions were adapted from a New York Times article "How to Meditate." Precise, clear and simple instructions are important for effectiveness and reproducibility. A different set of instructions were given for the meditation with and without the neurofeedback synthesizer and are as follows:

Instruction for Meditation Without the Neurofeedback Synthesizer

- Sit comfortably: Spine erect, not rigid. Alert and relaxed at the same time.
- Close your eyes, breathe deeply, loosen your body.
- Bring your focus to "The Third Eye" between your eyebrows, slightly higher than your eyebrows.

- Devote your attention to how you feel in your body and to your senses.
- When your mind wanders, gently bring your attention back to the sensations you experience without judgement.

Instruction for Meditation With the Neurofeedback Synthesizer

- Sit comfortably: Spine erect, not rigid. Alert and relaxed at the same time.
- Close your eyes, breathe deeply, loosen your body.
- Bring your focus to “The Third Eye” between your eyebrows, slightly higher than your eyebrows.
- Devote your attention to the sounds you hear, specifically the timbre and pitch of the sounds.
- When your mind wanders, gently bring your attention back to the sounds you are hearing without judgement.

Present moment awareness is based on senses that can be captured in real time by the brain, which is why the audio features indicated in the instructions are pitch and timbre. Noticing what is happening in the present moment is a key aspect of meditation. It allows the practitioner to be mindful, or “in the now” as some might say. It pulls the person’s mind away from its natural tendency to be caught up in the past or future. This is why almost instantaneously recognizable audio features were chosen to be mentioned in the instructions of the meditation test with neurofeedback.

Pitch can be noticed and everchanging in real time. Although it takes a certain amount of oscillations of hearing a sound wave to recognize the pitch of a sound, the time it takes to hear pitch is so small that it feels as though it is being recognized instantaneously once the sound is produced. This allows pitch to be a viable selection as an audio feature for a meditator to give their attention to while interacting with a neurofeedback device. Timbre is also an audio feature that can be recognized almost instantaneously. Thinking practically, pitch and timbre are features that people untrained in music are generally familiar with and can notice.

The technical set up for the experiment can be found in Figure 3, shown below. The participant wore an EEG headset, capturing signals from her forehead. The headset was connected to the MUSE App through Bluetooth. The muse app preprocesses raw data to derive clean power bands, visualizes data and sends data over OSC.

Figure 3: Meditation Experiment Technical Set-Up

OSC “was a technology designed, much the same as MIDI, for the audio industry. It was designed as a means of communication between computers, sound synthesizers and other multimedia devices, and optimized for modern networking... OSC is a content format, often referred to as a protocol, but only in the weakest sense, in that it defines a message format. Simply put, OSC does not define the semantics or language of a message, it only states how the message should be composed” (ETC Connect).

A larger image of the MUSE App interface can be found in Figure 4(a). Muse Lab receives OSC data from the app, visualizes data and forwards data over OSC to Max MSP. The information from this app is sent to MuseLab and used to control the synthesizer. The data from MuseLab was also captured for further exploration. The synthesizer was created in Max MSP and played through speakers. The synthesizer parameters update based on the “alpha ratio” captured from the data. The “alpha ratio” refers to the amount of alpha waves in relation to the other types of waves present. Figure 4(b) shows the Max MSP patch receiving data. The amount of each wave present in relation to one another is shown in the upper right hand side of the figure. In the figure, there are more alpha waves than delta, theta, beta or gamma waves. There is not a significantly higher amount of alpha waves in this instance.

Figure 4(a-b): Muse App and Max Patch

Within the Max MSP patch, the predominant band is detected, the alpha power band is derived and the data is smoothed. The alpha band is then mapped to synthesizer parameters. The user can unput their own music but, for this experiment, an ambient soundscape was used. The amount of alpha waves present in the signal varied the “aliveness” of the sound. More alpha waves correlated to a more dynamic sound and less alpha waves correlated to the production of a less active soundscape. In other words, the sounds became more calm when the user was calmer. This provided the user with feedback on their meditation, creating a preference for alpha waves. There have been studies that employ this technique as well as the opposite technique, creating more sound as the participant produces more alpha waves. I decided to create calmer music when the participant was producing more alpha waves.

During the procedure, Suvi mediated once without the neurofeedback device, once using the neurofeedback device and then she sang while wearing the headset that collected the EEG signals. It was thought that it might be interesting to compare brain waves while meditating to those while singing. These three different tests will be discussed and analyzed further below.

3.2. Singing

My data was retrieved in conjunction with another Sound and Music Computing master’s student, Suvi Häärä. We used the same participants and lead voice lessons

together. She used separate sensors for her thesis and I used EEG signals. In order to recruit participants, we made a flyer advertising our data collection needs as well as the benefits of attending a voice lesson. These flyers can be found in Figure 5. Two separate flyers were created, advertising our different needs and benefits to inexperienced and experienced singers. Many of the people who participated in the study were from our same master's program. Given that this program studies "Sound and Music Computing," most people had at least some experience with musical training.

Figure 5(a-b): Voice Lessons Flyers

A checklist was created to ensure a similar procedure with regards to each participant. I will explain the procedure here below. During the experiments, we used Suvi's iPad to look at the checklist, Suvi's laptop to log the answers to the questionnaire, take notes and record audio into Logic. My laptop was used to record video and audio in case video data or another stream of audio from a different location in the room proved to be useful for Suvi's experiment. My phone was also used to record video and audio for the same reason. My laptop captured a horizontal image and my phone captured a vertical image. The Biosignal data was collected through a computer given to us by UPF. We used a MIDI keyboard to conduct the voice lesson. The keyboard was connected to the

interface and we all wore headphones so we could hear the sound from the keyboard without the microphones picking up the keyboard sound. A microphone was used to capture sound closer to the participants and recorded through the interface on to Suvi's laptop. The relevant sensors for my thesis include the Biosignal EEG data as well as the audio signals.

The participants signed a consent form to allow us to use their data for this project, shown in Figure 6. We began by explaining the procedure and made time to let them ask us any questions they had about our projects and how we were going to use their data after reading the consent form. All participants agreed to the conditions presented in the form. We have collected all of their signatures and they were given the option to withdrawal from this study at any time should they chose that they would not like us to use their data.

Consent Form

Titles of Research Studies:
A Multimodal Dataset for Voice: Creating Technologies for Vocal Pedagogy
The Impact of Singing on the Nervous System.

Principal Investigators:
Suvi Haaeerae, Jessica Torrey, Dr. Raphael Ramirez

Invitation paragraph
You have been invited to participate in a research study. Please read the information provided in this form carefully before deciding. **Participation is voluntary**, and declining won't affect you. Feel free to ask questions or seek clarification.

What is the purpose of the study and what would taking part involve?
Case 1: Technologies for Voice Training
Some of the data will be used to train models to identify technical mistakes and 'good technique' while singing. This includes analysing audio, breathing patterns, laryngeal muscle movement, body posture and facial motion. This will potentially lead to the development of prototype technologies that support vocal lessons.

Case 2: Therapeutic Effects of Singing
Some of this data will be used to evaluate the effects of singing on the nervous system. This includes analysing brain activity as well as a survey taken by participants at the beginning and end of the study. This will potentially contribute data to the knowledge base used to evaluate music therapy techniques involving singing.

If you participate, you'll be asked to sing different phrases in various ways. First, in whatever way feels natural to you, then in ways where you deliberately have bad posture/make other errors, and finally when slightly modifying your tone by making it more breathy. While singing, data on audio, video, and biosignals are collected. You will also be asked a series of questions relating to your mental state and musical experience. Estimated time: 45 minutes.

Why am I being invited?
You have been identified as a potential participant, as we wish to collect data from people with various levels of experience with singing.

Do I have to take part?
This document has been written to help you decide if you would like to take part in this study. It is up to you whether you wish to do so. If you participate, **you are free to withdraw** without needing a reason, and with no penalties or detrimental effects.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?
The research aims to develop technologies supporting vocal pedagogy by studying how various factors affect voice quality and performance. Additionally, it seeks to understand how singing can influence the nervous system.

What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?
The study poses minimal physical or mental risk, and **you can withdraw at any time**. To minimize vocal fatigue, the task is kept short, and researchers will guide you during data collection. Your data will be fully anonymized and confidential. If you experience any negative effects, please contact the researchers.

Expenses and payments
There will be no expenses or payments required for participating in this study.

What information about me will you be collecting?
Data collected includes your experience level in vocal training, data from a Piezo-Electric Respiration (PZT) Sensor, an Electromyography (EMG) Sensor, two Electroencephalography (EEG) Sensors, audio, video and answers to questions relating to the tasks performed.

How will my data be stored and who will have access to it?
The data will be stored in an anonymous format, only accessible to the researchers of the study.

How will my data be used and shared?
The data will be used to write academic reports on multimodal vocal pedagogical technologies and the effects of singing on mental health.

Thank you for your interest in this research.

Please consider the following statements. Before signing the consent form, you should mark all or any of the statements that you agree with. Your signature confirms that you are willing to participate in this research, however, you are reminded that you are free to withdraw your participation at any time.

Statement	Please mark the box if you agree
1. I confirm that I have read the Information on this Consent form for the above study; or that it has been read to me. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have these answered satisfactorily.	
2. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to stop taking part in the study at any time without giving any reason and without my rights being affected.	
3. I understand that my data will be accessed by the investigator.	
4. I understand that my data will be securely stored following the data protection guidelines, in fully anonymised form.	
5. I understand that I can access the information I have provided and request the destruction of that information at any time before anonymisation (before leaving the data collection location). I understand that following anonymisation I will not be able to request withdrawal of the information I have provided.	
6. I agree to take part in the study.	

If you have any questions or concerns about the study or the data collected, do not hesitate to ask the research team.

Participant name _____ Date _____ Signature _____

Figure 6: Voice Lessons Participant Consent Form

After explaining the procedure and getting the participant's consent, we placed the sensors on the participant. A photo of myself with all of the sensors on me can be found in Figure 7.

Figure 7(a-b): Experimental Set-Up

To retrieve desired data, I attached EEG sensors to participants' foreheads. The sensors were from the company, OpenSignals. OpenSignals is an "easy-to-use and versatile software suite for real-time biosignals visualisation, compatible with all PLUX devices" (PLUX, OpenSignals). The sensors are labeled "Electroencephalography (EEG) Sensor" and I used two of them. They are "single-channel bipolar sensor[s]" and provide "medical-grade raw data output" (PLUX, Electroencephalography sensor). A GitHub repository was used to explore how to analyze the signals obtained, also created by Plux (PLUX, Biosignals Notebooks).

New gel pads needed to be placed on the sensors to ensure they would stick to the participants' foreheads and capture the signal. The EEGs did not work perfectly and some data needed to be discarded due to difficulties capturing the data, which will be addressed further in the discussion section of this thesis. Suvi required data collected by EMG (Electromyography) sensors so these were used during the procedure as well. Another sensor to measure breath was placed around the bottom of the participants rib cage to measure the frequency and depth of their breaths, as seen in the figure above.

The participants were asked questions regarding their biographical information, musical experience and current mental state. The participant's **Name**, **Sex** and **Age** were recorded along with the current date of their participation in the study. The following questions were asked of the participants:

- *The following describes my musical experience: 1 (No musical experience), 2 (Self-taught), 3 (Some musical education 1-5 years), 4 (Significant musical education >5 years), 5 (professional)*
- *Do you currently still play an instrument/sing?*
- *How many hours a week do you spend singing/playing your instrument?*
- *On a scale from 1-10, where 1 is easy and 10 is difficult, how difficult you think you will find the procedure?*
- *On a scale from 1-10, where 1 is badly and 10 is excellent, how well do you think you will do?*

I also administered a questionnaire based on the PANAS (Positive and Negative Affect) scale before and after the singing lessons. As introduced previously, this is a twenty question a self-report and findings from these questions will be explored in the results and discussion section of this thesis. It is a standard questionnaire used to gauge a person's current condition regarding a comprehensive range of common positive and negative feelings (Watson). My questionnaire was adapted from the one shown in Figure 2.

After these questions were asked of the participants, we double checked that our technology was working properly and all recorders were set up properly. We made sure my phone and computer were capturing the participants as needed and were ready to record. We performed a mic check with the participant to ensure we could reliably capture their audio throughout the procedure. I asked the participant to sing a comfortable note low in their register as well as a comfortable note high in their register to evaluate where they could perform the vocal exercises.

We then began by starting the collection of data upon alerting the participant that we were beginning to record. We started recording the Biosignal data, pressed record on Logic and then started the video recording on my computer and phone. We attempted to start these recordings at the same time but it was impossible to time everything perfectly

so we created a procedure to align the audio with the video and with the biosignal data. Before beginning to sing, we asked the participants to raise their eyebrows while simultaneously clapping. I am shown doing this in Figure 7(b). While this is not a perfect solution to data synchronization, it worked for our needs. The audio of the clap was captured by the microphone, my computer and my phone. The EEG sensors captured a peak upon the raise of the eyebrows. From there, the audio could be used to align the video and audio signals and the eyebrow raise could be used to align this video and audio with the biosignal data. This peak in the data sources could then be used to synchronize all of the data manually after the experiment. I did not end up using video data in my project but the synchronization was useful to align the audio files and biosignal data.

During the voice lessons, participants wore headphones to hear the piano and mimicked the scales they heard. I played the piano and Suvi sang the vocal exercises to exemplify how they should attempt to sound. She also assisted the participants when they had questions about the exercises or when troubles arose. Four different vocal exercises were given to the participants in order to explore different attributes of the voice. It was hypothesized that concentrating on different aspects of music (pronunciation of different vowels and consonants, simple and more difficult scales as well as staccato and legato notes) would affect a participants concentration and mood in different manners and provide a fairly comprehensive study of ways in which singers might use their voice while attempting to make the voice lessons relatively short in order to make our study more accessible to those with busy schedules. Each voice lesson was about 45 minutes.

The four vocal exercises that were performed are as follows, moving a semitone up after each exercise was performed without strain and stopped when the participant could not comfortably perform the highest notes necessary. The following excersizes are explained using note numbers in relation to the major scale.

1. An arpeggiation of a simple 3 note chord containing the root, major third and fifth (performed 1, 3 5, 3, 1) on the syllables “ma,” “me,” “me,” “mo,” “mu.”
2. An exercise containing the root, major second, major third and fifth (performed 1, 2, 1, 3, 1, 5, 3, 1) on the syllables “en,” “ge,” “en,” “ga,” “en,” “ga,” “o,” “u.”

3. Parts of a major scale (performed on 1, 3, 5, 8, 7, 5, 4, 2, 1) on a long “ru” sound, expressing the “ru” on the first note and then holding the “u” for the rest of the exercise.
4. An octave glissando (performed by sliding between all of the notes between 1 and 8, inclusive) on a hum.

After the exercises were done, we took a short break and performed physical exercises typically done in voice lessons. The participants moved their tongue around their teeth inside their mouths to activate muscles used during singing. They did neck rotations, moved their knees and checked their posture. They performed a long “hiss” sound to prepare their breath and performed a siren sound to explore their range. They then made a vocal fry sound activate their chest voice prior to beginning the second (and final) set of exercises. The same exercises listed above were performed again and then the participants were done with their lessons.

When the participants were done singing, we stopped recording data (turned off the Biosignals, stopped recording audio through Logic and stopped recording through my phone and computer).

The PANAS questionnaire was given once more and similar questions asked at the beginning of the experiment were asked at the end. These questions are as follows:

- *On a scale from 1-10, where 1 is easy and 10 is difficult, how difficult did you find the procedure?*
- *On a scale from 1-10, where 1 is badly and 10 is excellent, how well do you think you did?*

After all of the questions were answered, we removed the sensors from the participant and the procedure was over. We then removed the gel pads from the sensors to in order to use fresh ones with our next participants. We then saved all of the files obtained and complied them onto the same hard drive used throughout the experimentation process.

4. Results

4.1. Meditation

4.1.1. Electroencephalogram (EEG)

There were four different EEG sensors used in this experiment. The data from each of these EEG sensors are shown in separate graphs. The amplitude graphs show the actual wave forms captured and the spectrograms highlight the presence of certain frequencies. For the purpose of consistency throughout the analysis of the data (all of the data for meditation without music, with music and singing), the four EEG signals will be referred to as EEG1, EEG2, EEG3 and EEG4 and the spectrogram data will be referred to as S1, S2, S3 and S4 within each different section of this results chapter. When there is no music present, I will call the graphs NEEG1, NEEG2, NEEG3, NEEG4, NS1, NS2, NS3 and NS4. Relating to the section where Suvi meditated with music, I will refer to the graphs as MEEG1, MEEG2, MEEG3, MEEG4, MS1, MS2, MS3 and MS4. In the section regarding singing, the graphs will be referred to as SEEG1, SEEG2, SEEG3, SEEG4, SS1, SS2, SS3 and SS4. N is here to represent “no music,” M to represent “music” and S to represent “singing.” EEG, as expected, represents the raw EEG wave form and S is here to represent “spectrogram.” The numbers correspond to each EEG signal placed across Suvi’s forehead. The spectrogram graphs were limited on the y-axis to be below 40Hz because this doesn’t focus on higher oscillations associated with gamma waves and is more interested in alpha waves.

4.1.1.1. Meditation Without Music

Prior to beginning the meditation, much more noise is shown within the graphs. Once Suvi begins to meditate, there is much more consistency in the wave forms and spectrogram data. Below, Figure 8(a-h) shows graphs related to data collected while Suvi was meditating without the neurofeedback device, sitting in a quiet room.

Figure 8(a-h): Waveform Graphs and Spectrograms of Meditation Without Music Data

Figure 8(a,d) shows that the NEEG1 graph and NEEG4 graphs exhibit more noise prior to meditation. Suvi begins meditating around time stamp 120. During meditation, the amplitude of the waveform becomes smaller. NEEG2 and NEEG3 capture much higher amplitude signals. There are much clearer frequencies captured in NEEG2 and NEEG3 that can be used to support the suggested hypothesizes. NS1 and NS4 can be used to notice a difference between Suvi's brain activity prior to meditation and during meditation while NS2 and NS3 can be used to notice the presence of different frequencies that Suvi's brain is producing prior to and during meditation. Faint horizontal lines may also be noticed on NS1 and NS4. In graphs NS2 and NS3 it is noticeable that the horizontal lines around 9Hz (alpha waves) become more pronounced once Suvi begins meditating. However, there is also a lot of power in the horizontal lines around 21Hz and a little bit in around 17Hz.

4.1.1.2. Meditation With Music

Figure 9(a-h) shows similar graphs as were produced above correlating to the experiment where Suvi meditated using the neurofeedback synthesizer.

Figure 9(a-h): Waveform Graphs and Spectrograms of Meditation With Music Data

Again, here it can be seen that MEEG2 and MEEG3 exhibit higher amplitudes. There is also much more noise in the data prior to the start of mediation. MS3 shows a clear start of the meditation. There seems to be a faint noticeable horizontal line appearing during meditation around 12Hz this time in MS1 and MS4. There are powerful frequencies present in MS2 throughout the entire signal, even prior to meditation. There are also powerful frequencies present in in MS3 during meditation. These strong signals correspond to around 12Hz, 17Hz, 21Hz and 33Hz.

4.1.1.3. Singing A Song

Figure 10(a-h) shows similar graphs as were produced above. These graphs correlate to the experiment where Suvi sang a song she liked.

Figure 10(a-h): Waveform Graphs and Spectrograms of Suvi Singing a Song Data

It can clearly be seen that there is a discontinuity within the graphs. At some point the EEG sensors disconnected for some time and were not capturing signal. This is something to be expected when performing an experiment with real time sensors with human participants. These sensors are not always reliable and I was the only one in the room while Suvi was singing so I was not able to keep an eye on everything that was happening. As can be seen in the graphs, the problem was fixed after some time and the EEG sensors began capturing data again. Similar to before, SEEG2 and SEEG3 show a higher amplitude signal. SEEG1 and SEEG4 show lower amplitude signals. It can also be seen that the data is noisier throughout, as Suvi was not actively meditating. She was instead singing, which may produce more noise for multiple reasons. One reason is that she would not be completely still while singing. She must move her facial muscles and body in order to create the sounds she would like to with her voice. Another reason could be that she is focused on singing, which requires a different type of concentration

than meditation even though both mediation and signing produce a meditative feeling. There is not much that can be extrapolated from SS1 and SS4. However, SS2 shows clear noticeable frequencies at 11Hz, 17Hz and 21Hz. The band at 11Hz seems to get stronger over time while the bands at the other frequencies seem more consistent.

4.1.2. Positive and Negative Affect Schedule (PANAS)

Table 1 shows aggregates of the results of Suvi’s PANAS questionnaire during the testing.

	Interested	Excited	Strong	Enthusiastic	Proud	Alert	Inspired	Determined	Attentive	Active	Guilty	Hostile	Distressed	Upset	Scared	Irritable	Ashamed	Nervous	Jittery	Afraid	Positive	Negative	P - N	
Pre Meditation	4	3	2		3	3	2	3		3	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	2	1	28	12	16	
Post Meditation	3	1	3		2	2	2	3		2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	21	10	11	
Pre Neurofeedback + Meditation	4	2	2		3	2	3	2		2	3	3	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	3	1	26	13	13
Post Neurofeedback + Meditation	2	1	2		1	1	2	2		1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	15	10	5	
Pre Singing	3	3	2		2	2	2	2		3	3	3	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	3	3	25	16	9
Post Singing	3	3	3		2	2	3	3		3	3	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	2	1	27	12	15

Table 1: PANAS Meditation, Meditation + Neurofeedback, Singing

The dark green row of words are the positive affects and the dark red row of words are the negative affects. The first two rows of data report Suvi’s PANAS responses pre and post meditation. The next two rows of data below that report Suvi’s PANAS scores pre and post meditation with neurofeedback. The bottom two rows represent her scores before and after singing. The data does not confirm the hypothesis mentioned above. In fact, it seemingly contradicts the hypothesis. However, reasons for this will be addressed in the discussion section of this thesis. Suvi’s positive affect scores lowered after both meditation and meditation + neurofeedback. It increased after singing. On the other hand, Suvi’s negative affect scores also decreased with each intervention, as hypothesized. The decrease in negative affect was greatest after singing.

4.1.3. Short Answer Questions

Suvi also answered questions related to the following types of meditation: Meditation without Neurofeedback, Meditation with Neurofeedback and Singing.

- Question 1 (asked after meditation without neurofeedback): *How well do you think you meditated?*

Suvi’s response: “It was easier in the beginning. Towards the end, I was thinking about how long 5 minutes is. My brain started wandering. I haven’t meditated in a while.”

- Question 2 (asked after meditation with neurofeedback): *How well do you think you meditated?*

Suvi's response: "I think it was different from before. With this one, it was harder in the beginning and easier towards the end. It took a bit of time to get used to the soundscape. Once I got adjusted to that, it was kind of easier to have a sound to focus on."

- Question 3 (asked after both meditation sessions): *How useful was the neurofeedback for the meditation?*

Suvi's response: "In the beginning, I was thinking about how my brain affected the sound. I think it depends on where your state of mind is on the day. I've meditated since I was a toddler... I think it's interesting to see how it works differently for different people. It was easier to have something to focus on. A sound might have a different effect on people that think in images"

- Question 4 (asked after singing a song of her choice, "The Man That Got Away by Judy Garland): *How do you think singing effected your mood?*

"It was similar to meditating in a sense that you're kind of focusing your energy on a task and making your body work for the task. I like singing so I am always in a good mood when I get to sing, especially when I manage to sing well."

4.2. Singing

4.2.1. Electroencephalogram (EEG)

Figure 11(a-h) shows the data retrieved from the EEG signals during the voice lessons. The data is incredibly messy and doesn't show any consistencies in terms of brain waves present. There is data available for all participants but only two participant's data are shown in the figures.

Figure 11(a-h): Voice Lesson EEG Waveforms and Spectrograms From Two Singers

As can be seen, there are no clear patterns of brain waves present. This is unfortunate and indicates that the data was not collected accurately even though the waveform graphs looked as they should have during testing. The data from the other participants look similar.

4.2.2. Positive and Negative Affect Schedule (PANAS)

An aggregated version of the collected data from the participants based on these questions can be found in Table 2. Each row of the table is a different participant and the values in the table represent the change of the effect from before versus after the voice lesson. For instance, if a participant answered a 3 for how “interested” they were prior to the voice lesson and then 4 after the voice lesson, the number corresponding to the participant in the “Interested” column in the chart would read 1 to represent the difference. Negative numbers indicate the feeling was decreased after the voice lesson.

1. Interested	3. Excited	5. Strong	9. Enthusiastic	10. Proud	12. Alert	14. Inspired	16. Determined	17. Attentive	19. Active	2. Distressed	4. Upset	6. Guilty	7. Scared	8. Hostile	11. Irritable	13. Ashamed	15. Nervous	18. Jittery	20. Afraid
0	1	0	1	1	-1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	-1	-1	0	0
0	0	0	0	2	2	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	-2	0	-1	2	-2	0	0	-2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-1	-1	0
0	0	2	0	3	-2	2	-1	2	0	0	0	-1	0	0	0	0	-3	-3	-1
1	1	-2	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	-1	1	1
0	0	-1	-1	0	-1	0	0	-2	-1	0	0	-1	0	0	0	0	-2	-2	0
0	-1	0	-1	-1	0	-1	3	0	-2	-1	-1	1	0	-1	0	0	-2	-2	0
0	1	0	0	1	-1	-1	1	0	0	-1	0	-1	0	-1	0	0	-1	0	-1
1	1	0	0	0	0	-1	0	0	0	-2	-1	-1	-2	-1	0	-1	0	-1	0
-4	-4	-4	-5	-3	-3	-3	-4	-4	-3	-2	-1	-1	-2	-1	-2	-1	-1	-2	-1
0	0	0	0	1	-3	1	0	-1	0	-2	-1	0	0	0	0	0	-1	-1	-2
0	0	-1	0	-2	-1	-1	-1	-1	1	0	0	-1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
0	1	2	-1	-2	0	1	4	-1	-1	0	0	0	0	-2	-1	0	0	0	0
-1	-1	-1	0	-1	0	-2	-1	0	-1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	2	2

1. Interested	3. Excited	5. Strong	9. Enthusiastic	10. Proud	12. Alert	14. Inspired	16. Determined	17. Attentive	19. Active	2. Distressed	4. Upset	6. Guilty	7. Scared	8. Hostile	11. Irritable	13. Ashamed	15. Nervous	18. Jittery	20. Afraid
-2	-4	-6	-5	8	-13	-4	0	-3	-4	-5	0	0	-7	1	-2	-4	-15	-5	2
1	-1	-1	-1	8	-4	3	2	-1	0	0	-1	1	-1	0	0	-1	-10	-6	0
-3	-2	-5	-5	-3	-8	-5	-4	-6	-2	-6	-3	-2	-2	-6	-2	-2	-3	-3	-4
-1	0	1	-1	0	-2	-2	0	4	-2	0	1	0	0	0	-1	-1	0	2	2

Table 2: Voice Lessons PANAS Data

Table 3 Represents the tallied data, adding up all of the positive scores as well as the negative scores.

Positive Affect (Before)	Positive Affect (After)	Negative Affect (Before)	Negative Affect (After)	PA - PB (+ is more positive feelings)	NA - NB (+ is more negative feelings)
29	33	13	11	4	-2
23	30	10	10	7	0
28	23	17	15	-5	-2
30	36	18	10	6	-8
30	39	21	13	9	-8
41	44	11	15	3	4
42	36	14	10	-6	-4
39	37	31	24	-2	-7
32	35	18	12	3	-6
33	32	13	27	-1	14
35	36	33	24	1	-9
36	44	24	23	8	-1
32	29	21	15	-3	-6
33	38	14	10	5	-4
29	21	14	21	-8	7
24	18	14	15	-6	1
27	28	14	10	1	-4

Table 3: Positive Affect and Negative Affect Totals, Before and After Lesson

Positive Affect Analysis:

- Most participants show an increase in positive affect after the experiment, indicating a positive emotional response to the singing intervention.
- A large amount of participants show a decrease or not much of a change in positive affect, suggesting a varied impact of the intervention.

Negative Affect Analysis:

- Many participants show a decrease in negative affect after the experiment, indicating reduced negative emotions.
- A few participants exhibit an increase in negative affect, suggesting that the intervention may have different effects on different individuals.

The PANAS scores before and after the experiment suggest that the singing intervention generally has a positive impact on the participants' emotional states, increasing positive affect and decreasing negative affect for most participants. However, individual responses can vary, and further analysis could explore the reasons for these differences. Unfortunately, the alpha score (in statistics, not brain waves) related to the data collected being too low and the general variance between experimental data led to inconclusive results. Nonetheless, I will still analyze and give insights into why the results may be what they are and comment on nuances from the data.

Figure 12(a-c) show the aggregate data from the PANAS questionnaires of the participants. Figure 12(a) shows the data after it has been normalized to account for the amount of participants being represented. Figure 12(b) highlights the differences between the participants who are beginner singers versus intermediate or professional singers. Figure 12(c) highlights the differences between the data of the male and female participants. These graphs were created to explore, corroborate and highlight findings made by previous researchers in the field.

All Participants (Normalized Data)

(a)

Beginner vs. Intermediate/Professional Singers (Normalized Data)

(b)

(c)

Figure 12(a-c): PANAS Data Aggregation Graphs

The word “proud” showed the largest increase and “nervous” showed the largest decrease overall. “Alert” also showed a substantial decrease. There was also a noticeable decrease correlating to “scared,” “jittery” and “distressed.” There was no overall significant increase in any other category. As is recognized by Figure 12(b), the decrease in “nervous” and increase in “proud” largely came from data from beginners. Beginners reported feeling more “inspired” while intermediate/professional singers reported feeling less “inspired” overall. It is also recognized by Figure 12(c) that the increase in “proud” after voice lessons was due to the female singers. Therefore, female beginners seemingly experienced the most benefits. Male singers overall felt less nervous, attentive and alert overall. None of the data points for the differences in any of the categories matched up for the two professional singers besides “active.” However, this is just one similarity, likely based in coincidence. These results and the implications of these results will be further analyzed in the discussion section of this thesis.

5. Discussion

5.1. Choice of Questionnaire (PANAS)

I did some more research into psychological questionnaires after realizing that different questions may have allowed me to achieve more telling results. The PANAS questionnaire allowed me to gauge how people were feeling but there is a natural tendency to become more calm during meditation. While this is a positive feeling, the PANAS questionnaire doesn't tell the full story.

For example, during the meditation experiment, if Suvi was feeling more calm in general after meditating, she may have self-reported a lower score when assessing feelings like "excited" and "enthusiastic." When analyzing each data point, it is apparent that this is what happened. Because she was feeling less excited and enthusiastic after meditation, which is expected, she still scored lower with regards to the positive feelings on the questionnaire. After performing more research about the questionnaire after realizing these discrepancies within the experiments, it became more clear as to why it might not achieve significant results. Research was done to find a reliable test for positive and negative feelings, which I thought would be useful when analyzing meditation data. However, when digging deeper into sources that criticize the PANAS questionnaire, the following was found in relation to previous studies:

"Often, research uses the PANAS to measure responses to situational manipulations of emotion, and often null effects are reported. Because emotions are only probabilistically linked to measures of emotion, it is inappropriate to assume that a null effect on a self-report measure means that emotional processes were not involved in the psychological phenomena of interest. That is, the (often poor) measurement of emotion should not be conflated with emotion itself. Emotion can be involved in driving a phenomenon despite null effects on measures of self-report." (Fell)

Looking back at the words used in the PANAS questionnaire, it can be shown that the language doesn't take excitement/arousal into account as much as it does valence. This didn't allow for as much of a detailed approach towards measuring meditative states as would be ideal, as meditation often involves changes in both valence and

excitement/arousal. “Emotional valence describes the extent to which an emotion is positive or negative, whereas arousal refers to its intensity, i.e., the strength of the associated emotional state.” (Feldman) The PANAS test used in my experiment took valence into account but failed to account for the extent that changes in arousal effect emotional state. Figure 13 Gives a two dimensional representation of arousal and valence and corresponding emotions at various levels of both attributes. As can be noticed through analyzing the PANAS questionnaire and the arousal and valence graph, the questionnaire mostly takes into account high arousal states and compares valence.

Figure 13: Arousal vs. Valence

Image: Lima, R., Chirico, A., Varandas, R., Gamboa, H., Gaggioli, A., & Bermúdez i Badia, S. (2024). Multimodal emotion classification using machine learning in immersive and non-immersive virtual reality. *Virtual Reality*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10055-024-00989-y>

While the PANAS questionnaire is commonly used in studies like mine, the results are also often complex and do not paint the full picture of a participant’s mental state. Nevertheless, using this questionnaire as well as studying it’s use cases and flaws was a valuable learning experience that I will take with me as I embark on future studies and experiments. I must both remember to take into account all of the drawbacks of specific questionnaires. Prior to this experiment, I was not familiar with creating these types of studies so this learning experience has been eye opening. Measuring emotion is difficult in general and the use of self-reported data proved to be a challenge to analyze scientifically with a small sample size.

If I were to perform this experiment again, I would instead propose the use of the Discrete Emotions Questionnaire (DEQ), discussed in *The Discrete Emotions Questionnaire: A New Tool for Measuring State Self-Reported Emotions*, as it provides more insight into both the valence and arousal of the participant in a more nuanced manner. With more time and resources, it would have also been interesting to create various iterations of the study and perform this study with more participants, refining the questionnaires, scales and analyzation techniques used upon new discoveries.

5.2. Meditation

5.2.1. Electroencephalogram (EEG)

The spectrogram data for meditation without music, meditation with music and singing all produced bands at 17Hz and 21Hz. The bands are also present throughout the whole time of the experiment. This could indicate that they are a product of the device itself. It may have noise that produce these frequencies. However, the band in the alpha range seems to vary. Meditation without neurofeedback produced a stronger band at 9Hz, while meditation with the neurofeedback device produced a more defined band closer to 12Hz and singing produced a fainter band, also closer to 12Hz. These observations are of value because it was expected that all three types of meditation would produce alpha waves and they did. However, the data suggests that meditation with the neurofeedback device was able to encourage Suvi to focus harder. The band present at around 34Hz is strange and more research into the MUSE device or EEG analysis may be needed to explain this. It does not fit into any hypothesis that Suvi would be producing a frequency at 34Hz during a neurofeedback meditation session. However, this discovery could lead to future research in the field but it may just be an anomaly in the data.

Simply meditating seemed to produce a slightly lower frequency of alpha waves. However, this could also be due to how Suvi was feeling before meditation without music and meditation with music. It is difficult to achieve conclusive data in an environment where there are multiple factors at play that could be affecting the data aside from the desired experiment. In all of the experiments, alpha waves were detected, as hypothesized.

If this data is accurate, it could be interesting to conduct more research or experiments related to the power of alpha waves and the types of alpha waves produced through different methods of meditation. However, given the time constraints towards the end of the research, no other participants were found to test the device. With more participants, consistencies between parameters produced by different participants could be more telling than using data from a single source.

5.2.2. Positive and Negative Affect Schedule (PANAS)

5.2.2.1. Meditation Without Music

The only score that increased between before and after regular meditation was Suvi's self-reported score for the word "strong." Initially, she reported a score of 2, then a score of 3. All other points remained the same or decreased. As a whole, her positive score decreased from 28 to 21. Her negative score decreased from 12 to 10, as shown in Table 1 In the results section.

5.2.2.2. Meditation With Music

Here, none of the scores increased. The overall decrease in the scores was even more drastic with the positive effect, decreasing from 26 to 15 and the negative affect decreasing from 13 to 10.

As discussed previously, it makes sense that her excitement/arousal score would have decreased in both experiments with and without neurofeedback and I should have included more questions related to differences in arousal/excitement in the questionnaire. The meditation with neurofeedback appears to have a greater effect on her. However, the numbers do not exhibit statistical significance. While the data is not conclusive, it gives insight into ways that this experiment can be adapted to create results that are more reliable.

5.2.2.3. Singing A Song

Here, "strong" increased from 2 to 3, "alert" increased from 2 to 3, "inspired" increased from 2 to 3. The rest of the scores decreased. The overall positive score increased from 25 to 27 and the overall negative score decreased from 16 to 12. Based on the test, it appears as though singing had an overall positive effect but, again, the results

are not statistically significant. As is the case for the other studies, the inclusion of excitement/arousal may have shown more powerful results with relation to the similarities between meditation and singing on a single participant.

Although some useful data can be extracted from her answers to the PANAS questionnaire, it is her qualitative responses that I am more interested in. The raw data for the PANAS scores as well as Suvi's responses to the questions asked of here are both found in the results section of this thesis.

5.2.3. Short Answer Questions

5.2.3.1. Meditation Without Music

When meditating without neurofeedback, Suvi felt as though it became more difficult to clear her mind towards the end and she was thinking about the time. Her brain started wandering and she felt more distracted as time went on. This is typical of someone who hasn't meditated in a while. Entering a meditative state can be quite difficult, especially if someone hasn't practiced before or doesn't practice regularly. This is where interventions and neurofeedback devices come into play.

5.2.3.2. Meditation With Music

Here, Suvi's answers were typical with regards to other studies relating to neurofeedback. It is common for people to attempt to control a device they encounter or focus too much on their own mind rather than the activity at hand when they are provided direct and real time feedback about their mental state (van der Kolk). Suvi has meditated before and has her own insights and notions about the practice. She found it easier to concentrate for longer when she had a sound to focus on, as hypothesized. This supports the initial hypothesis qualitatively. While subjective questions aren't a measurement to definitively validate the hypothesis in this case, it does provide valuable insight.

5.2.3.3. Singing A Song

In her discussion about singing, Suvi pointed out an important aspect of why studying voice lessons could be so valuable. Suvi felt good after singing and gained energy overall. She saw a clear connection between singing and meditation and noted that she was focusing her "energy on a task" and making her "body work for the task."

Meditation involves focused attention, necessitates energy/discipline/practice and reveals a strong connection between the mind and body. While this answer is biased based on what Suvi knew about the test, she gave this information freely and honestly without anyone asking her to make her own connections between meditation and signing. While this also supports theories related to the meditative qualities of signing, these qualitative results are not enough to convulsively validate the hypothesizes presented.

There is long standing knowledge that meditation as well neurofeedback interventions improve mental capabilities. However, the study of using music, specifically the voice is a newer field of study. By creating a connection between meditation and singing, I aimed to highlight the mental health benefits of meditation and, in turn, also highlight the mental health benefits of signing, as they are both practices that bring the mind and body to the present moment.

5.3. Singing

5.3.1. Electroencephalogram (EEG)

Features from the EEG data were extracted and analyzed. There were some tests in which the sensor data became disconnected, the sensors weren't correctly placed on the participants head, the sensors were not firmly stuck to the participants head and other complications that caused some data to be unusable. The data needed to be cleaned and feature extraction methods needed to be determined to analyze the data. However, even with data analyzation methods employed, the data did not appear to produce any viable information.

It is likely that the EEG sensors used in the meditation study were more robust than the ones used in the study about voice lessons. The sensors used in the voice lessons study may not have worked as well. The Biosignals used also did not offer a way to check to see if the EEG data was being well received. There must be a way to figure out how to verify the reliability of the sensors. However, given this was my first time conducting an experiment like this, I was not privy to all of the ways that things could go wrong during the data collection process.

If I were to perform this experiment again, I would have used EEG sensors like those used in the meditation study or found a way to be notified if the sensors were not

producing viable data. I also wish I had checked the data using spectrogram analysis prior to completing the study with the participant's used. The study was taking place during a hectic moment in time and I wish I spent more time validating data throughout the process. Nevertheless, the experimental design and procedure as well as the results and errors made has allowed me to realize many things about the process of conducting a long term study with sensitive and human based data. Looking back at the methods for using the EEG sensors, it appears as though they were used in the correct manner. However, the data indicates otherwise. More experimentation and research into why this is the case would be useful to understanding the nuances of why the data turned out the way it did.

5.3.2. Positive and Negative Affect Schedule (PANAS)

Breaking down the PANAS data into multiple groups, the differences between beginners and intermediate singers as well as the differences between male and female singers may be explored further. Looking at prior research mentioned in the state of the art, amateur singers tend to feel more well-being compared to professionals after a singing session (Grape). Male and female singers differ in the sense that females tend towards feeling a sense of more well-being after a singing session, while male singers have self-reported feeling worse after a singing session in previous studies. (Stephen Clift)

It should be noted that there are 7 beginner participants and 6 non-beginner participants. There are only 5 male participants here, compared to 8 female participants. The demographics of the study may play a role in the results and upon further research, it would be useful to congregate a group of people comprising of a similar amount of males and females to more accurately test the hypothesis relating to gender.

In this study for, beginners showed a greater increase in positive effect as well as a greater decrease in negative effect, indicating an overall greater well-being compared to intermediate and professional singers. The beginners reported feeling a much greater increase in "proud" and a much greater decrease in "nervous" and feeling "jittery," more specifically. It appears as though intermediate/professional singers also experienced a greater decrease in "alert" and "inspired." This is consistent with previous research, as it has been shown that professional singers show less positive excitement and it is hypothesized that this is due to the fact that they may sing for work and don't find singing as novel as beginners (Grape).

With regards to gender, female singers showed a greater increase in positive effect, however, male participants showed a greater decrease in negative effect. In more nuanced terms associated with the specific data, the females in this study felt a greater sense of “pride” after a singing session, while the males felt a greater decrease in “nervousness.” Figures 12(c) and 12(b) in the results section show the numerical data related to these findings from this thesis experiment. The findings relate to but don’t directly correlate or support previous research.

While it is interesting to compare this research with previous findings, many changes should be made to the experiment in order to ensure reproducibility, consistency and attention to detail that would validate the data’s viability and actually contribute to general knowledge about hypothesizes related to the well-being of singers relating to their skill level and gender. Overall, singers seemed to feel better but the type of questionnaire used, the sample size and the demographics of this experiment don’t allow the hypothesizes to be validated for certain.

6. Conclusion

6.1. Meditation

Future work expanding on the study involving meditation and neurofeedback could be to include an analysis of all of the different types of brain waves present while meditating. There could be a more complex synthesizer created using values produced by the whole spectrum of brain waves in order to create a preference towards alpha waves at the beginning of meditation and then theta waves once the practitioner has been meditating for a while. This project used a signal processing approach. However, more complex and meaningful features could possibly be extracted using a machine learning approach. Another consideration when expanding on this project could be an exploration of more sonification methods. Perhaps the user could be presented with natural sounds (such as wind blowing, rain falling, birds chirping, ocean waves crashing...), as they provide calming affects.

Another way this experiment could be expanded upon would be to conduct these experiments on groups of people, as each individual is different and may respond to sounds in different manners and to different capacities. While it was interesting to explore how an individual would perceive this neurofeedback technique and how it would affect their mental state, it would have been more scientifically significant to perform this experiment on a group of people and notice similarities and differences between participants' responses. Suvi mentioned in one of her responses that it might be interesting to conduct the study on groups of people who think in images versus words and analyze the similarities and differences they experience when working with the neurofeedback device. It could also be more telling to perform this study with advanced practitioners of meditation as the participants. The amount that one has practiced meditation generally correlates to their abilities to control their mental states. This could allow them to be more open to neurofeedback techniques. However, this could also mean that they might be better at controlling their mental states without the need for neurofeedback. Overall, there are many ways in which this study could be expanded upon.

Overall, this study provided the chance to explore psychology, meditation, mindfulness, neuroscience, EEG signals, real time data analysis, sound synthesis, brain waves in relation to their corresponding mental states, audio feature analysis,

experimental procedures involving Bluetooth and OSC, Max MSP, music therapy and more inspiring topics. While the data was not perfect, a lot was learned in the process of researching these various topics, testing theories, collaboration with participants/classmates, analyzation of data and the documentation of results.

6.2. Singing

While I learned a lot through the process of experimental design, data collection and analysis, there are many things that could have been different in order to obtain more reliable results with regards to the voice lesson experiment.

Limiting the sample of participants to have a specific background to create less independent variables could have created more telling data. This type of test has a lot to do with the participants. If I were to conduct this experiment again, I would want to collect from a larger sample size and try to collect data from an equal number of people of different genders as well as skill levels. I would also want to include people of different ages. All of the participants were a similar age due to the people both Suvi and I knew in Barcelona. However, it took a lot of time to run the experiments and it was difficult to find enough participants, let alone participants with a specific background, to participate.

Studies involving diverse demographic groups to understand the universal and specific benefits of singing would be ideal. It is crucial to explore how factors such as age, gender, cultural background, and musical experience influence the effects of solo singing on mental health. This will help identify which populations might benefit most from singing-based interventions. I could have also attempted to work with participants experiencing diagnosed anxiety or depressive symptoms to incorporate more specific hypotheses related to mental health.

Another possibility for future work could include the use of a full EEG headset that captures more areas of the brain. I could have also been interesting to find sensors related to more qualities of participants during singing, such as, skin conductance, heart rate immune response and more. This could lead to more investigations into the underlying mechanisms by which singing influences mental health, including hormonal, neurological, and immunological pathways. Understanding these mechanisms could lead to the development of targeted interventions that harness the specific benefits of singing for various mental health conditions. However, these sensors and experiments can be

expensive. Also, using more devices necessitates a more complicated experimentation process, which could add extra time to the study and may sway people away from wanting to participate.

If I had more of a budget, I could have also brought in a professionally trained vocal coach to conduct the voice lessons. However, this, again, adds more expenses to the project.

Similar to the study relating to meditation, I would have used a different questionnaire if I were to conduct a similar study with voice lessons again. The questionnaire did not meet the needs of my hypothesis to the extent that I thought it would. While this does not provide the type of data I wanted, there is a lot to be gained and learned from this recognition. I could have also asked more subjective questions to get feedback from the participants about how they think the voice lessons made them feel in their own words, rather than just relying on the number-based questionnaire.

I learned a lot from performing the research I did and by running the experiment. However, it would have been useful to have enrolled in one of UPF's psychology courses in order to get more input from professionals in a field of science relating to psychology/neuroscience/emotions. It may have also been useful to have taken the course, Sound Communication, prior to the last trimester of UPF's master's program, as I found a lot of the information presented in that course to be useful to my thesis project but I didn't incorporate all of it because I began experimentation prior to taking this class. I now have a better understanding of how EEG sensors work, physically as well as with regards to the type of data they can collect. This opens many doors for possible future experiments about mental states as I embark on new endeavors related to psychology.

Future research should address the existing gaps and explore new areas, such as, longitudinal studies. Long-term studies would assess the sustained impact of singing on mental health and well-being. Longitudinal research could provide valuable insights into how the benefits of solo singing evolve over time and whether continued practice leads to cumulative or diminishing effects.

The development and evaluation of digital singing interventions to expand access to therapeutic benefits could also be an important topic to explore. As digital technology continues to advance, it offers new opportunities for remote and accessible mental health

interventions. Exploring how virtual platforms can replicate or even enhance the benefits of in-person solo singing will be an important area of future research.

As these experiments required a lot of time, attention to detail, set up and planning, it worked well to collect data in conjunction with Suvi. It took a lot of time to run the experiments and a lot was learned through the process of creating such a long term study. While there are many things that could have been done differently, the learning experienced gained through this process has been incredible.

It might be interesting to attempt to perform this experiment again using different types of EEG sensors in a controlled environment and over a longer period of time. The hypothesis that solo singing would produce higher amounts of alpha waves in the brains of the participants needed to be discarded due to the data collected. It is most likely a viable hypothesis that can be tested in the future. However, this study could not validate it.

Overall, solo singing did raise self-reported positive effects and lower self-reported negative effects for the most part and there are many known benefits to solo singing. However, the data is inconclusive for reasons discussed previously.

In conclusion, there are many things I would have done differently if I had known what I know now. I learned a lot throughout the process of research, experimentation, iteration and analyzation of data. Conducting research with human participants poses challenges that I am glad I got to face and work through. Conducting research relating to psychology, EEGs, brain waves, singing and teaching allowed me to combine many of my interests. The knowledge I gained from this experience has been incredibly valuable, even though the results weren't very telling. I will be able to use what I learned about psychology, physiology, teaching, singing, meditation, anxiety, depression, mental health, questionnaires, electroencephalograms and much more in future studies, projects and endeavors.

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